

Deep-sea records of shells of *Argonauta nouryi* Lorois, 1852 (Mollusca, Cephalopoda, Argonautidae) in western Mexico

Registros de conchas de *Argonauta nouryi* Lorois, 1852 (Mollusca, Cephalopoda, Argonautidae) en aguas profundas del Pacífico mexicano

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ABSTRACT

Empty shells, also known as egg cases, of females of the epipelagic cephalopod *Argonauta nouryi* were collected in deep sea off the coast of western Mexico, in two localities at 1535–1542 m and 1858–1879 m depth. A total of 30 shells (length 28 to 53 mm), most of these entire, were examined and represent the second record of *A. nouryi* empty shells in deep sea, below 200 m depth. It is suggested that entire shells found on the sea bottom indicates that the individuals were not consumed by apex predators but rather died of natural causes or penetrate into the very shallow, wide, hypoxic or even anoxic core of the Oxygen Minimum Zone, a habitat hostile for the argonauts which feature high metabolic rate and high aerobic demand.

Key words: Argonauts, paper nautilus, empty shells, eastern Pacific

RESUMEN

Se recolectaron conchas vacías, conocidas también como cascos para huevos, de hembras del cefalópodo epipelágico *Argonauta nouryi*, frente a las costas del Pacífico mexicano, en dos localidades en profundidades de 1535–1542 m y 1858–1879 m. Se examinó un total de 30 conchas (largo de 28 a 53 mm), la mayoría intactas, lo que representa el segundo registro de conchas de *A. nouryi* en el mar profundo, por debajo de los 200 m. Se sugiere que estas conchas intactas encontradas en el fondo del océano son un indicador de que los individuos no fueron consumidos por depredadores ápice, sino que murieron de causas naturales o penetraron en el núcleo hipóxico y hasta anóxico de la Zona del Mínimo de Oxígeno que, en esta área, es muy somera y muy amplia y representa un

hábitat hostil para los argonautas que poseen un metabolismo alto y una demanda aeróbica muy alta.

Palabras clave: Argonautas, nautilus de papel, conchas vacías, Pacífico Este

INTRODUCTION

The genus *Argonauta* Linnaeus, 1758, comprises of non-migrators, holoepipelagic species distributed mostly in epipelagic tropical and subtropical waters (Alejo-Plata & Martínez Santiago 2020, Judkins & Vecchione 2020). All their life phases occur in the epipelagic zone where adult females begin to brood eggs at smaller sizes and continue feeding, growing and producing eggs as they age and are found at the surface during the day, dusk, and night (Finn 2016, Shea 2023). They are also known as argonauts or paper nautilus because of the shell-like eggcase, where females carry the eggs until they hatch (Mitchell et al. 1994, Checa et al. 2021, Battaglia et al. 2021).

The genus contains only four species: *Argonauta argo* Linnaeus, 1758, *Argonauta hians* [Lightfoot], 1786, *Argonauta nodosus* [Lightfoot], 1786, and *Argonauta nouryi* Lorois, 1852 (Alejo-Plata & Martínez Santiago 2020, Battaglia et al. 2021), all recorded in western Mexico, in the eastern Pacific (Finn 2016, Landa Jaime et al. 2018, Alejo-Plata et al. 2019). Taxonomic history of the genus is very complex with about 50 species names proposed mostly in the 18th and 19th centuries now recognized as junior synonyms of the four currently accepted species (Alejo-Plata et al. 2019, WoRMS editorial board 2025). Males of *Argonauta*, often called dwarf males, are of very small size, about 1/8 compared to females size and, contrary to females, do not construct a thin, spirally coiled shell.

Argonauts feed on jellyfishes, heteropods, pteropods, other species of cephalopods, crustaceans, and fishes (Heeger et al. 1992, Sukhsangchan et al. 2009). Like many other members of the Cephalopoda, females of species of *Argonauta* represent an important item in the food chain of fish, marine mammals, and occasionally birds (Olson & Galván-Magaña 2002, Galván-Magaña et al. 2006, Markaida & Sosa-Nishizaki 2010, Osuna-Peralta 2014, Landa Jaime et al. 2018, Alejo-Plata et al. 2019, Briones-Hernández et al. 2019). Consequently, the soft tissues are digested by the predators and the shell is reduced to small pieces. Some studies have reported on the presence of species of argonauts in the stomach of freshly collected fishes (Alejo-Plata et al. 2014 and references therein), as in western Mexico where the species of *Argonauta* were the second most represented group of Cephalopoda. Most identification, however, were based on characteristics of the beaks (Alejo-Plata et al. 2019). During sampling activities in deep water off the SW coast of Mexico, shells of argonauts were collected with a benthic sledge in deep water. This material is reported herein.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The material reported herein was collected during the TALUD XII, deep-sea research cruise (April 2008) aboard the R/V “El Puma” of the Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México (UNAM), off the SW coast of Mexico. Specimens were collected with a standard benthic sledge (2.35 m wide × 0.95 m high) equipped with an outer collecting net of about 5.5 cm (2.25 inch) stretch mesh and an inner net of about 2.0 cm (0.75 inch) stretch mesh. Trawling at the stations reported herein lasted 30 min at an average speed of 1.75 knots. Swept area was obtained using the trawling distance (average speed x trawling time) and sledge width. Sampling depths were estimated with a digital SIMRAD echo sounder. Epibenthic temperature and oxygen concentration were measured near bottom level with a Seabird CTD-O2 probe. Oxygen concentrations were double-checked with the Winkler method using water samples collected in closing bottles near the bottom. Oxygen profiles in the water column were drawn using the CTD-O2 probe data at sampling stations and completed with data from a slightly deeper adjacent profile (section in red in the profile). All the specimens examined are deposited in the Regional Collection of Marine Invertebrates at the Mazatlán Marine Station, UNAM, Mazatlán, Mexico (ICML-EMU-catalogue number). Measurements follow Finn (2018). Abbreviations: St. station; ShL, shell length; ShB, shell breath.

RESULTS

Taxonomy

Class Cephalopoda Cuvier, 1795

Order Octopoda Leach, 1818

Family Argonautidae Cantraine, 1841

Argonauta Linneaus, 1758

Argonauta nouryi Lorois, 1852

Figures 1, 2

Material examined. Two samples collected on the continental slope, off the state limit between Colima and Michoacán, SW Mexico (Fig. 3). TALUD XII, St. 24 (18°28'00"N, 104°14'10"W), April 1, 2008, benthic sledge, 1535–1542 m, 2 empty shells (ShL 28 and 34 mm; ShB 17 and 18 mm) (ICML-EMU-14106); St. 25 (18°26'45"N, 104°16'10"W), April 1, 2008, benthic sledge, 1858–1879 m, 28 empty shells, 8 partly damaged (Table 1) (ShL 27–53 mm; ShB 16–35 mm) (ICML-EMU-14207).

Common names. Rough-keeled argonaut; argonaute tuberculé; argonauta tuberculado (Finn 2016).

Distribution. Epipelagic (surface to 20 m depth). In the eastern Pacific *Argonauta nouryi* has been recorded from southern California, USA, and the Gulf of California, western Mexico, south to off Peru (Finn 2016); originally described from the Marquesa Islands, it occurs from western America throughout the Central Pacific, roughly to 140°W (Finn 2016).

Figure 1. *Argonauta nouryi* Lorois, 1852. ICML-EMU-14207. Size: ShL 53 mm, ShB 35 mm. A, lateral view; B, ventral view; C, dorsal view.

Remarks. Most shells obtained in the benthic samples were entire (Table 1; Fig. 2); some were slightly damaged, with part of the shell being broken. This indicates that the animals from which the shells belonged to were not consumed by predators, in which case shells would have been fragmented (see Alejo-Plata et al. 2019). One hypothesis is that specimens probably died of natural causes, including a mass postreproductive mortality when females complete their reproductive cycle. Females of species of *Argonauta* form large aggregations at the surface (Okutani & Kawaguchi 1983, Rosa & Seibel 2010). Shelled females of *Argonauta nouryi* have been observed attached to one another, forming chains (or strings) of individuals (Rosa & Seibel 2010). High mortality rate among dense, postreproductive aggregations of females might explain the presence of numerous shells on the sea bottom in a single locality.

Table 1. Measurements of *Argonauta nouryi* collected during the survey.

TALUD XII Est. 24 (n=2)	ShL (mm)	ShB (mm)	Damaged
1	34	18	NO
2	28	17	NO
TALUD XII Est. 25 (n=28)	ShL (mm)	ShB (mm)	Damaged
1	53	35	NO
2	39	29	NO
3	44	30	NO
4	33	21	NO
5	38	24	NO
6	32	20	NO
7	29	18	NO
8	35	21	NO
9	31	19	NO
10	32	20	NO
11	45	29	NO
12	38	25	NO
13	33	21	NO
14	42	26	YES
15	37	23	YES
16	34	20	YES
17	36	24	YES
18	39	23	NO
19	31	19	NO
20	30	15	NO
21	31	19	YES
22	31	19	NO
23	29	16	YES
24	27	16	NO
25	27	18	NO
26	29	17	NO
27		17	YES
28		23	YES

Figure 2. *Argonauta nouryi* Lorois, 1852. ICML-EMU-14207. Specimens (24 out of 28) not or only slightly damaged. Sizes in Table 1.

The eastern Pacific is characterized by a very strong, vertically wide Oxygen Minimum Zone (OMZ) extending from the USA to northern Chile (Helly & Levin 2004). It is particularly extensive off western Mexico, with core values of 0.2 ml O₂/l or even less (Serrano 2012, Papiol et al. 2016). Therefore, another hypothesis is that specimens of *A. nouryi* accidentally migrated into the OMZ that extends off Colima and Michoacán, where central core strong hypoxia (< 0.2 ml O₂/l) or even anoxia prevail (Helly & Levin 2004, Serrano 2012, Papiol et al. 2016).

Records of *A. nouryi* in the eastern Pacific appear to be mostly restricted to shallow waters (Finn 2016, Landa Jaime et al. 2018), above the OMZ central core. According to Rosa & Seibel (2010), the metabolic rates for argonauts are clearly higher than those reported for deep-living holoplanktonic octopods and they are much more dependent on high oxygen concentration in their natural habitat. Based on their oxygen consumption and high aerobic demand, Rose & Seibel (2010) suggested that the vertical distribution of *A. nouryi* in the eastern tropical Pacific is restricted to oceanic regions with high oxygen levels. Critical oxygen deficiencies (< 0.2 ml O₂/l) at shallow depths (i.e., from 22 m and deeper) recorded in the water column in the area (Fig. 4) where the shells were collected might explain the presence of entire shells at bottom due to the death of individuals caused by severe

hypoxia, their sinking across the entire OMZ, and the subsequent consumption of body tissues by benthic scavengers. Dissolved oxygen concentrations recorded near bottom level (below the OMZ) at the two localities where empty shells were dredged, 0.95 ml O₂/l (St. 24) and 1.39 ml O₂/l (St. 25) respectively, are high enough to allow for the existence of several groups of small scavengers (e.g., Amphipoda, Pandalidae) (Windfield et al. 2017, Hendrickx 2022) to survive and consume the soft parts of the argonauts, leaving the shells intact or almost intact.

Figure 3. Localities where the specimens of *Argonauta nouryi* Lorois, 1852 were collected during the survey.

Empty argonauts egg cases, or paper shells have been previously observed on the seafloor in deep sea (Nesis 1977, Hoving et al. 2022). Nesis (1977) reported the presence of shells of *A. boettgeri* Maltzan, 1881 (a junior synonym of *A. hians*) in bottom trawls in trenches in the W Pacific Ocean, but did not provide further details related to this occurrence. Hoving et al. (2022) reported 200 intact, empty shells (ShL average, 5.84 cm ± 1.8 cm; maximum ShL, 12.75 cm) likely belonging to *A. nouryi* using seabed images datasets obtained in the Clarion Clipperton Zone, Central Pacific, at depths of 3970 to 4551 m. Material reported by Hoving et al. (2022) is larger than maximum ShL reported by Finn (2016): 94 mm. Our material maximum ShL was 53 mm and maximum sampling depth 1879 m. Hoving et al. (2022) estimated a maximum density of 61.7 egg cases (or shell) per hectare (ha). Using the swept area method, samples obtained at station 24 (2 shells) and at station 25 (28 shells) in this study correspond to estimated densities of 6.16 and 86.2 shells/ha, respectively. As stated by Hoving et al. (2022), medium-size carcasses of cephalopods are rapidly consumed by scavengers. Therefore, observations of remains of this group of marine animals in deep water are extremely rare and present report appears to be the third available for a species of argonaut, especially considering the depth at which the samples were collected. When they reach bottoms >1000 m depth, shells of argonauts dissolve by three months and contribute to input of CaCO₃ in the benthic ecosystems. This is particularly important in deep sea where there is an undersaturation of CaCO₃ (Hoving et al. 2022).

Empty shells of *Argonauta* have been observed in great numbers stranded on shore, e.g., along the coast of Uruguay, in the western Atlantic (Demicheli et al. 2006: *A. nodosa*). Other records are for the Strait of Messina, Sicilia (Battaglia et al. 2023: *A. argo*), SE Tasmania (Grove & Finn 2014: *A. argo*), and the southern Gulf of California (Gonzales-Peralta 2006: three species). Demicheli et al. (2006) attributed this unusual event to a

combination of oceanographic and meteorological conditions that advected oceanic warm waters toward the shore. Battaglia et al. (2023) noted events of particular hydrodynamic regime and upwelling currents off this area, which allows the stranding of mesopelagic, uncommon and rare fauna. Grove & Finn (2006) hypothetically related the finding of *A. argo*, a species rarely occurring in Tasmanina waters, with an unusual pulse of warm water. Three species of *Argonauta*, *A. cornuta*, *A. pacifica*, and *A. nouryi*, females of *A. nouryi* being the most abundant, have been observed stranded on beaches in the southern Gulf of California, Mexico, during late winter and early spring (January to March) (Gonzales-Peralta 2006, Finn 2016), a season close to our observations. Gonzales-Peralta (2006) assumed stranding occurred when females ascend to the surface and are washed up on beaches by strong winds and water coastal currents. The southern Gulf of California also experiences a very strong impact of a shallow, wide OMZ, with subsurface, epipelagic oxygen concentration values $< 0.2 \text{ mlO}_2/\text{l}$ below 89 m (Hendrickx & Serrano 2010). In the southeastern part of the Gulf, on the mainland coast, upwelling are frequent and strong during winter, bringing nutrient-rich but oxygen-deficient waters near surface (Lluch-Cota 2000, Lavin & Marinone 2003). Although there are no direct data related to the impact on argonauts population, a negative effect of these upwelling on their survival seems reasonable considering their low tolerance to oxygen-deficient environment.

Figure 4. Dissolved oxygen profiles recorded at the two localities where specimens of *Argonauta nouryi* Lorois, 1852 were collected. Arrows indicate the depths of collection.

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